

INFORMATION ON MEASURING INSTRUMENTS USED IN ENERGY AUDIT AND ANALYSIS OF THE DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THEM

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Annotatsiya : Indicator measuring instruments are used in energy audits. These devices are mainly divided into 2 types: analog and digital measuring devices. Currently, digital measuring devices are mainly used in energy audits. We will introduce some of these tools.

Keywords: export, operation, highway, defectoscopy and substation

Tipi -Portaflow 330

Pipe diameter: 50...1000 mm, liquid flow speed: up to 20 m/s determines the consumption and speed of liquid flow in heat and water supply. In particular, heat transfer fluids in the boiler room; drinking water in the water supply system; It is designed to measure water supply in technological lines

Tipi - Portaflow D550

Pipe diameter: 50...1000 mm, liquid flow speed: up to 20 m/s determines the consumption and speed of liquid flow in heat and water supply. In particular, heat

transfer fluids in the boiler room; drinking water in the water supply system; It is designed to measure water supply in technological lines

Analyzers measuring the quantity and quality of electric energy parameters

It is used to determine the indicators of the quality of electricity in electrical networks, to check measuring and recording devices, to select filtering and covering devices, to determine the points of loss of electricity, to identify malfunctions of electrical equipment, and to construct active and reactive electricity consumption graphs. designed for measuring, recording, calculating and analyzing alternating current parameters in single-phase and three-phase circuits.

Type - AR. 5L. Measuring range of voltage: 0...500 V (four outputs), current: 0...2000 A (four outputs), detects up to 49 harmonic constituents, effects and detects fast processes and measures the current in the neutral wire.

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